

A Sol–Gel based magneto-optical device for the NANOSAT space mission

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Abstract On December 2004, the Spanish Space Agency INTA (Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial) launched the first nanosatellite called NANOSAT (Fig. 1) on board an European rocket Ariane 5, from the French Guyana. The satellite consists of a hexagonal device of 19 kg of weight with a diameter of about 50 cm, which describes a LEO orbit of 655 km of altitude. The main objective of the satellite is to probe the operation and performance of micro- and nanotechnologies in space environment. One of the scientific experiments implemented on board was the Sol–Gel based magnetic nanosensor.

Keywords Space applications ·
Magneto-optical nanosensor · Sol–Gel

1 Introduction

The magnetic Sol–Gel nanosensor will be responsible for the positioning and orientation of the satellite by the detection of the Earth gravitational magnetic field. The sensor consists of a dispersion of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ magnetic nanoparticles in a transparent silica matrix prepared using the Sol–Gel procedure. This nanocomposite, exhibiting the

magneto-optical Faraday effect, was implemented as the heart of the magnetic-nanosensor. The complementary systems, such as the detection optics and the electronics required for the operation of the nanosensor, were developed accord to the requirements and performance of the nanosensor. The design of the nanosensor and the complementary systems should also comply with the strong vibrations imposed by the launch procedures and the harsh space environmental conditions. The nanosensor was designed for a lifetime of 3–6 years in orbit. Tests are currently being carried out to check the performance of the nanosensor in-orbit, under the extreme environmental space conditions. From the results obtained from through nanosensor, we consider that from the point of view of Sol–Gel technologies, the development of an advanced device from its chemical design in the laboratory to its implementation into a satellite, now in orbit, is a very promising achievement, and encourages us to continue collaborating in future scientific space missions.

In this special issue devoted to Prof. Avnir, we report for the first time this interesting development that we hope can promotes Sol–Gel materials and technologies one step ahead in the field of materials science for space applications.

2 Objectives of NANOSAT

NANOSAT 01 is mainly a technological experiment that combines low-consumption electronics, digital processing of signals, nanostructured materials, and an innovative satellite design, in which no distinction is made between

Fig. 1 NANO-SAT 01

platform and payload (Fig. 2). The external faces of the satellite are covered by high performance solar cells that, together with ion-lithium batteries, provide all the power required by the satellite (see Fig. 3).

Based on the experience of multidisciplinary scientific and technological research groups on nanotechnology led by INTA, we are able to show here the general design of an earth magnetic nanosensor, which has been fabricated and integrated on the NANO-SAT. A Sol-Gel based magneto-optical sensor was designed and developed to measure the gravitational parameters of the Earth and allow the orientation of the NANO-SAT.

Fig. 2 Objectives of NANO-SAT

Fig. 3 Inside view of the NANO-SAT

3 Sol-Gel preparation of the magnetic nanosensor

The heart of the magneto-optical device is a Sol-Gel prepared Faraday rotator, consists of a dispersion of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles in an amorphous silica matrix.

When light propagates along the axis of a transparent rod, the application of an axial magnetic field to the rod causes a rotation of the plane of polarization of the light, due to the interactions between the light and the magnetic field (Fig. 4).

$$b = \frac{1}{4} V B d;$$

where b is the angle of rotation, B is the magnetic flux density in the direction of propagation, d is the length of the path where the light and magnetic field interact, and V is the Verdet Constant for the material. This empirical proportionality constant varies with wavelength and temperature.

Fig. 4 Faraday effect

In order to obtain an effective magneto-optical performance, the $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ nanocomposite material should comply with the following requirements [1]:

- Superparamagnetic nanoparticles (particle size ≤ 15 nm), to avoid remnant magnetization of the particles
- High transparency, to allow measuring the rotation of the light polarization plane
- High Verdet constant, to obtain a measurable rotation
- Good mechanical properties, to allow its integration in a magneto-optical device.

The $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ doped silica nanocomposites were prepared following a procedure described elsewhere [2, 3], starting from $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), resulting in a material having a Fe/Si molar ratio of 0.18. The gels were then heated to 400°C for 4 h to obtain hard brittle solids. The $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ was grown in situ during the thermal treatment.

3.1 Properties of the $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ magnetic nanoparticles

The composite obtained shows dispersed nanometric $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ particles in an amorphous silica matrix, as shown in the TEM micrograph given in Fig. 5. The average particle size as estimated from the TEM pictures is 10 ± 2 nm.

The nanocomposite shows very high transparency in the near IR region of the spectrum, as shown in Fig. 6, allowing the measurement of the Faraday rotation using LED emitting in that range (700–900 nm).

According to their macroscopic magnetization behavior, the particles embedded in the silica matrix behave as a super paramagnetic material, in accordance with their particle size (~ 10 nm). The magnetization curve of the magnetic nanocomposite is given in Fig. 7. The XRD diffraction patterns of the composite show the existence of

Fig. 5 TEM images of $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{silica}$ composite

Fig. 6 Near IR transmission spectrum of the $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ nanocomposite

a clean $c\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ phase having an estimated particle size of 11 nm (Fig. 8), dispersed in an amorphous silica matrix. This estimation is in concordance with the particle size observed in the TEM micrographs.

3.2 Magneto-optical device

In order to work as a sensor for magnetic fields, the nanocomposite should be stacked between a single polarizer and a set of four polarizers with their axis oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ and -45° with respect to the first one, forming a polarimetric detection scheme, as shown in Fig. 9. The light beam emitted by a LED is polarized, and its polarization plane rotated by the magnetic nanocomposite. This rotation is detected as an optical intensity change, thanks to

Fig. 7 Magnetization curve of the c-Fe₂O₃ doped silica nanocomposite

Fig. 8 X-ray diffraction patterns of the magnetic nanoparticles

the stack formed by the four polarizers and the array of four detectors (quadrant photodiodes).

The magneto-optical device has approximately 20 mm of diameter and less than 5 mm of thickness. It contains several coils for the sensor self-calibration (in order to compensate the possible drifts of the Verdet constant due to temperature or wavelength changes). The sensor head is composed of three magneto-optical devices to measure the magnetic field in the three spatial coordinates. The control electronics include a stabilized current source for the LED and a phase detection stage for the signal. According to the mission specifications, the nanosensor has a low mass (about 20 g for the sensor head and about 200 g for the control electronics) and a low power consumption (~ 2 W).

3.3 Faraday rotation in Sol-Gel prepared nanocomposite

The Faraday rotation of the Sol-Gel prepared nanocomposites was measured at the Space Instrumentation Laboratory (LINES) at INTA [4]. In order to improve the mechanical properties of the c-Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites and reduce the light depolarization, the samples were embedded in an acrylic resin and polished to obtain plates with thickness from 0.2 to 1 mm as shown in Fig. 10. The Faraday rotation of the c-Fe₂O₃/SiO₂ based nanosensor as a function of the induced magnetic field is given in Fig. 11. The material showed a Verdet constant of $-0.0353^\circ\text{G}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$, being substantially larger than that of other high-Verdet bulk materials such as terbium gallium garnet or iron-doped PMMA having Verdet constants of -0.0077 and $-0.006^\circ\text{G}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

3.4 Magnetic field amplifiers

The earth magnetic field signal at a 655-km orbit is quite small, and should be amplified in order to increase the sensitivity of the measurement. An amplifier attached to the nanosensor resulted in a 20-fold increase in the sensitivity of the measurement. The magnetic field required for a 0.1-mV change in the nanosensor signal was 0.0073G and 0.15G with and without amplifiers, respectively. The magneto-optical response of the Faraday rotator with and without magnetic field amplifiers is shown in Fig. 12.

3.5 Extreme space conditions

The magnetic nanosensor will be exposed to harsh environmental conditions in space. Therefore, the materials have to be designed taking into consideration, the several environmental issues such as the space radiation (protons, electrons, UV), extreme temperatures changes and high vacuum conditions in space. The hard conditions that the device must resist during launching (strong vibrations, etc.) are also part of the space qualification tests, and should also be taken into consideration in the design of the device.

3.6 Space qualification tests

The devices to be loaded in space missions should undergo a strict space qualification testing procedure in order to assure satisfactory performance on-board. The procedure includes the physical measurements and performance test of the device. The device is then tested for vibrations, thermal vacuum and thermal cycling testing procedure. The performance of the device is checked by the after each test. Then, an electromagnetic compatibility testing is done followed by final performance tests and a final inspection.

Fig. 9 Schematic representation of the magneto-optical device

Fig. 10 Processing of the composite material to prepare samples for magneto-optical measurements. a The composite sample as obtained; b the composite is embedded in an acrylic resin to improve

mechanical strength; c the sample is polished to specific thickness (0.2–1 mm) needed for the magneto-optical measurements

Fig. 11 Faraday rotation of the c-Fe₂O₃/SiO₂ composite

Fig. 12 Signal versus magnetic field measured by the magneto-optical device

After the space qualification test, the sensor units are built-up, including connectors and crystalline covers, to be integrated into NANOSAT. The performance of the c-Fe₂O₃/SiO₂ Nanosensor is evaluated, including the

development and testing of associated software and defining functionality tests and alignment procedures. Finally, a laboratory testing of the devices is carried out by testing its dynamic range and performing an electronic optimization.

4 Conclusions

A Sol–Gel-derived magneto-optic nanocomposite consisting of a dispersion of magnetic nanoparticles in a silica matrix was successfully implemented in a magnetic nanosensor based on the Faraday effect. The nanosensor is currently responsible for the orientation of the Spanish research NANOSAT satellite with respect to Earth.

This important achievement is the result of a close and fruitful joint research venture, of 7 years between the National Institute for Aerospace Technology and the Materials Science Institute of Madrid.

We hope that this first Sol–Gel based technological development, now in-orbit, will open new possibilities to apply the enormous potential of the Sol–Gel technology to the design of new materials for challenging space applications aiming to the miniaturization of the satellites, in order to reduce payloads and high costs of space mission.

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